

Original Research Article

In-service training programmes and mentoring for improving teachers' job performance in North Senatorial District of Ondo State, Nigeria

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Abstract

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It has been observed that teachers, particularly junior ones, in public secondary schools do not perform their instructional and non-instructional tasks satisfactorily. This could be as a result of inadequate exposure to in-service training and lack of mentoring by principals and senior teachers in the teaching profession. This study therefore examined in-service programmes and mentoring as determinants of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Ondo Senatorial District, Nigeria. The descriptive research of the survey type was adopted. The sample consisted of 324 respondents that were selected using multistage procedure. Two questionnaire instruments entitled "In-service Training and Mentoring Strategies Questionnaire (ITMSQ)" and "Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire (TJPQ)" were used for data collection. Two research questions were raised and answered using frequency count, percentage and mean while two hypotheses were formulated and tested using Pearson Product Moment Correlation at 0.05 alpha levels. Findings revealed that that teachers perceived in-service training as a tool that moderately improve teachers' capacity; there was a significant relationship between in-service programmes and teachers' job performance; and a significant relationship existed between mentoring strategy and teachers' job performance. Based on the finding, it was concluded that both in-service and mentoring strategies contribute positively to teachers' job performance in public secondary schools. It was recommended, among others, that Government should encourage teachers to access capacity training within and outside the school by giving monetary assistance and due recognition to participants.

Keywords: In-service training programmes, mentoring, teachers' job performance, public secondary schools.

INTRODUCTION

Resources were observed to be a major contributive factor in the provision of quality education (Ajibade, 2005). Among school input factors, teachers' job performance come foremost. If teachers are not well equipped to teach effectively, quality education may not be hindered. Consequently, the effectiveness of a society could be majored by the quality of the education impacted in student. Researchers have observed that teachers are not dedicated to their calling which seems to

have affected their performance in terms of instructional delivery, use of instructional materials, classroom management and student assessment/ evaluation which appear to be rampant among teachers in public secondary schools in South western Nigeria (Adebayo, 2011; Fasasi and Ojo, 2014).

It seems that teachers represent grate potency in the educational system because their job performance are especially linked to learning outcomes of the student and

the education system. The inconsistency of student performance in public examinations in Ondo state maybe ascribed to teachers whose performance of teaching and consequently learning have not been proven with clear success.

However, the reasons for low performance of teachers could equally be associated to resource allocation and the failure to build teachers capacity significantly. Adukwu-Bolujoko (2010) noted that Nigerians are known for attending seminars, workshops and conference but locally and internationally but courses selected for these training programmes do not adequately cater for the needs of such individuals. This condition poses serious threat to the education system because the quality of teachers in schools may determine the quality of students they produce. Therefore, to improve teachers' skills, knowledge and competencies there is need for constant and appropriate training or re-training of teachers, provision of necessary resources, materials and infrastructure that will foster sustainable teachers' commitment to effective teaching and learning. Researchers have attempted investigations into improving teachers job performance using in-service training and mentoring strategies such as workshops, conferences, seminar and information and communication technology (ICT) trainings (Fasasi and Ojo 2014; Uchendu, 2015).

In-service training programme entails continuous updating of teacher's knowledge, skills and interests in chosen field through workshop, seminar and conferences. Asiyai (2016) posited that teachers' in-service training can be described as a catalyst capable of driving positive changes in rganiza, boosting their morale and their job commitment. In a survey of teachers who have benefitted from in-service training programmes, Ogunrin (2011) reported that teachers generally believe that in-service training programmes are very useful to them in terms of professional development, capacity building and productivity.

In-service training is the process of constant updating of teacher's knowledge, skills and interests in chosen field (Nakpodia, 2008). It is a means for continuous professional growth, which encourages the extension of technical assistance by teachers' educators. In-service training is an integral part of staff development programme which is organized for teachers while in service through workshops, seminars, and conferences among others. Akinbode (as cited in Asiyai, 2016) discovered that in-service training of teachers is closely related to the development of job commitment. It was observed that teachers who had low commitment to the teaching profession prior to training became highly committed after they were given opportunity to participate in in-service training.

Teachers like medical doctors, ministers, and lawyers, must continue with their education after graduation. The

need to constantly apply new techniques and materials makes education in service absolutely necessary. If teachers are to become real leaders in their various schools, they must be equipped with a programme of in-service training which is concerned with doing and not merely with listening (Amadi, 2011). Also, Ogunrin (2011) reiterated the need to train and retrain teachers already on the job to reshape their orientation towards qualitative education.

The training of teachers is one of the pillars of sustainable development and national capacity building in any country in the world. The desired educational reform cannot be achieved through curriculum in terms of subject taught and school infrastructure alone without considering teachers' capacity to cope and meet classroom challenges in order to respond positively to the growth and developmental needs of the students. In-service training mediums exposes teachers to variety of professional development opportunities that includes; curriculum support, study groups and induction programs (Jaquith et al., 2010).

Yusuf et al. (2017) confirmed that teachers who had acquired workshop programmes are more equipped and have the intellectual capacity to impart adequate knowledge on their students. Asiyai (2016) revealed that through in-service training programmes, teachers learnt new methods, skills and techniques which impacted positively on their instructional practices. A significant number of teachers agreed that in-service training improved their knowledge of teaching approaches, using representations, models, diagrams and new questioning approaches.

The origins of mentoring initiatives for teachers in schools can be traced back to the school reform movements in the 1980s. During these movements, policy makers and educational leaders advocated for mentoring as a strategy to retain the newly qualified teachers by allowing them access to capable senior teachers who could induce them into the new environment (Van der Walt, 2016).

According to Idoko et al. (2016), mentoring in education is a process of learning and development based on a personal relationship in which an experienced teacher called a mentor helps a new teacher called mentee to develop as a professional and achieve professional goals. Mentoring relationship differs from other types of personal relationship because it is a developmental relationship embedded within the career context. Mentoring can help the new teacher put theoretical knowledge into practice, apply rganizatio concepts to specific responsibilities and become familiar with given job situations (Pan and Hovde, 2010). The two main views of mentoring identified were formal mentoring, and informal mentoring. Formal mentoring is a formally structured programme that includes peer, group and electronic mentoring. It is designed to facilitate

mentoring relationships in an organization or a professional association. Mentees are matched with mentors based on parameters set by administrators. The organization oversees and guides the mentoring programme in order to promote employee development. They are usually structured, have clear and specific goals and can be assessed.

Informal mentoring refers to one-to-one relationship where selection is dependent on the personal choice of either the mentor or the mentee. It happens spontaneously based on mutual respect and rapport when someone with more experience takes a special interest in the career of a less experienced colleague who he organizes as having potentials or talent. It can also happen when a less experienced individual approaches an experienced senior colleague who he believes can help him gain new knowledge and skills (Spencer, 2010).

Idoko et al. (2016) noted that informal mentoring is widely being practiced in academics among all levels of staff because the practice is more or less like apprenticeship. Their findings revealed that informal mentoring allows the individual participants to decide the terms of their relationships without organization input. The result indicates that informal mentoring, which is usually unplanned, unstructured and without the involvement of any organization is the main strategy in use for professional development in Nigeria. Ekechukwu and Horsfall (2015) posited that academic mentoring plays an intensive role in education to bring about quality in a teacher. When a less experienced teacher is being taught by an experienced teacher, it signifies mentorship especially when there is a follow-up on the part of the mentor and/or mentee. They further explained that mentoring could empower the continuous and lifelong development of teachers.

The findings of Jepketer et al. (2015) revealed that most teachers agreed that mentoring equipped teachers with necessary skills, knowledge and competencies in their subject areas, articulated their teaching areas, and enabled them to perform better. The study further showed that capacity building strategies improves teachers' teaching skills in their subject areas, widens teachers' pedagogical experience and strengthens teaching competences enabling them grow as professional teacher.

An experimental study conducted by Achor and Duguryil (2014) which investigated the effectiveness of a teacher mentoring programme in enhancing teacher's attitude towards the teaching profession found out that mentored teachers (experimental group) had higher mean post-test score than the control group. The test of difference using analysis of covariance implies that mentoring is effective in changing teachers' attitude towards the teaching profession.

However, Moemeke et al. (2012) empirically discovered that mentoring has positive effect on mentees'

teaching competency level. The level of competency of teachers after exposure to expert mentors indicated that the use of expert mentors often records better results. The mentors stressed student empowerment and belongingness as effective classroom management tools. Furthermore, mentors addressed issues related to school personnel such as teacher retention, professional development, support, building collegial relationships, adjusting inconsistencies in school policy implementation, and classroom problems.

Statement of the Problem

Inadequate in-service training and mentoring have been identified by education stakeholders as a factor undermining the job performance of teachers in public secondary schools. Findings from previous studies showed that teachers have not effectively carried out their duties which seems to have affected instructional delivery, use of instructional materials, class management, attendance to lessons, and lateness to duty which may have negative effect on students' academic performance.

It seems that the level of teachers' job performance in public secondary schools may have accounted for the inconsistency of students' performance in public examination in Ondo State. The number of candidates that obtained five credit passes including Mathematics and English is not consistent.

In view of this milieu, this study investigated the relationship between in-service training, mentoring strategies and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Ondo North Senatorial District of Ondo State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide this study:

1. How do teachers perceive in-service training strategy in public secondary schools in Ondo North Senatorial District?
2. How do teachers perceive mentoring strategy in public secondary schools in Ondo North Senatorial District?

Null Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were formulated to guide this study:

1. There is no significant relationship between in-service training programmes and teachers' job performance.
2. There is no significant relationship between mentoring and teachers' job performance.

METHODOLOGY

The survey design was adopted for the study. Multi stage sampling procedure was used to select three local government areas from the six existing local government areas in Ondo North Senatorial District of Ondo State. Three hundred and twenty-four respondents were drawn comprising principals, heads of department and teachers from six secondary school's samples from each of three local government areas making total of 18 public secondary schools in Ondo North Sectorial Districts. Two instruments entitled "In-service Training and Mentoring Strategies Questionnaire (ITMSQ)" and "Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire (TJPQ)" were used for data collection. The instrument was structured on 4 point Likert rating scale categorised strongly Agreed =4, Agreed=3, Disagreed=2, Strongly Disagreed=1 respectively.

The two instrument were face validated by two experts in tests and measurements unit, Department of guidance and counselling in the faculty of Education of Adekunle Ajasin University, Akungba-Akoko. The research instruments were trial tested through test-retest method in two public secondary schools in Local Government Area that was outside the study.

Frequency counts and percentages were used to answer research questions while Pearson Product Moment Correlation was used to test the hypotheses to determine the tenacity of the relationship between the independent and dependent variables at 0.05 significant levels.

RESULTS

The results of data analysis were presented in two parts. Research questions were answered descriptively using frequency counts and percentages while hypotheses were tested with inferential statistics tool specifically Pearson Product Moment Correlation at 0.05 alpha level.

Research Question 1

How do teachers perceive in-service training strategies in public secondary schools in Ondo North Senatorial District?

Data collected on in-service training as rated by teachers were used to answer the first research question. The results were presented on Table 1 to show the level of teachers' perception of in-service training in public secondary school in Ondo North Senatorial District.

The analysis of data on Table 1 showed that 49.6% of the respondents indicated that they have been given opportunity to attend seminar/ workshop/conference in the last three years while (50.4%) of the respondents

indicated they have not been given the opportunity to attend seminar/ workshop/conference. However, 82.2% of the respondents agreed that they learnt new strategies in lesson planning while 17.8% felt otherwise. The majority of the respondents (85.6%) supported the statement which says that they acquired new skills in teaching difficult concepts while 14.4% opposed that claim. It was also indicated that 84.1% of the respondents were of the opinion that they learnt modern techniques in classroom management while 15.9% felt contrary. On a similar note, 85.2% of the respondents affirmed that they acquired better skills in the use of instructional materials while 14.8% negated the claim. Lastly, 74.8% of the respondents also affirmed that continuous assessment techniques were practically discussed while 25.2% negated the statement.

The summary of responses by average of the percentage showed that 77% of the respondents agreed that in-service training have enhanced their job performance in core aspect including lesson planning, teaching difficult subjects, classroom management, effective usage of instructional materials and continuous assessment techniques while 23% felt otherwise. The average of means value of 2.95 implied that teachers perceived in-service training as a tool that moderately improve teachers' capacity.

Research Question 2

How do teachers perceive mentoring strategies in public secondary schools in Ondo North Senatorial District?

The analysis of data on Table 2 showed that 67.1% of the respondents affirmed the statement that inexperienced teachers were paired with experienced teachers in mentoring while only 32.9% negated the statement. Similarly, majority of the respondents (87.1%) also supported the claim that mentors guided the mentees in preparation of lesson notes while only 12.9% opposed. It was also indicated that 90.3% affirmed that experienced teachers guided new teachers in assessing the performance of their students, however, 9.7% felt contrary. Similarly, 90% of the respondents were of the opinion that mentoring strengthened interpersonal relationship. In similar vein, 85.2% of the respondents agreed that experienced teachers provided practical knowledge for new teacher on classroom management while 14.8% disagreed. On a final note, 87% of the respondents affirmed that mentoring accelerate learning capacity of teachers while 13% felt otherwise.

The summary of responses by average of percentage showed that 84.5% of the respondents affirmed that teachers in secondary schools in Ondo North Senatorial District of Ondo State were exposed to mentoring which improve capacity. The average of means value of 3.17 implied that mentoring as a capacity building strategy

Table 1. Teachers' Perception of In-service Training.

S/N	Items		Response					
			SA	A	D	SD	\bar{x}	
1	I have been given opportunity to attend seminar/ workshop/conference in last 3 years	F	20.0	114.0	79.0	57.0	2.36	
		%	7.4	42.2	29.3	21.1		
2	I learnt new strategies in lesson planning	F	62.0	160	28.0	20.0	2.98	
		%	23.0	59.2	10.4	7.4		
3	I acquired new skills in teaching difficult concepts	F	72.0	159	30.0	9.0	3.09	
		%	26.7	58.9	11.1	3.3		
4	I learnt modern techniques in classroom management	F	89.0	138	29.0	14.0	3.12	
		%	33.0	51.1	10.7	5.2		
5	I acquired better skills in the use of instructional materials	F	95.0	135	32.0	8.0	3.17	
		%	35.2	50.0	11.8	3.0		
6	Continuous assessment techniques were practically discussed	F	73.0	129	60.0	8.0	2.99	
		%	27.0	47.8	22.2	3.0		
Percentage Average/ Av. of Means			F	69	139	43	19	2.95
			%	25.5	51.5	15.9	7.1	

Table 2. Teachers' Perception of Mentoring.

S/N	Items		Response					
			SA	A	D	SD	\bar{x}	
7	Inexperience teachers are paired with experienced teachers in mentoring	F	59.0	122.0	74.0	15	2.83	
		%	21.9	45.2	27.4	5.6		
8	Mentors guides the mentees in preparation of lesson notes	F	85.0	150.0	28.0	7.0	3.16	
		%	31.5	55.6	10.4	2.6		
9	Experienced teachers guides new teachers in assessing the performance of their students	F	107.0	137.0	22.0	4.0	3.29	
		%	39.6	50.7	8.2	1.5		
10	Mentoring strengthens interpersonal relationship	F	104.0	139.0	26.0	1.0	3.28	
		%	38.5	51.5	9.6	0.4		
11	Experienced teachers provide practical knowledge for new teacher on classroom management	F	92.0	138.0	40.0	0.0	3.19	
		%	34.1	51.1	14.8	0.0		
12	Mentoring accelerate learning capacity of teachers	F	103.0	132.0	31.0	4.0	3.24	
		%	38.1	48.9	11.5	1.5		
Percentage Average/ Av. of Means			F	92	136	37.0	5.0	3.17
			%	34.0	50.5	13.7	1.8	

was moderately used in the study area.

Hypothesis One

There is no significant relationship between in-service training programmes and teachers' job performance.

To test hypothesis 1, data collected on in-service training programmes and teachers' job performance were extracted and subjected to Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient at 0.05 level of significance. The result is shown in Table 3.

The result in Table 3 indicated that r_{cal} 0.682 is greater than r_{tab} 0.195. This implies the existence of a significant relationship between in-service programmes and teachers' job performance at 0.05 level of significance and 322 degree of freedom. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no relationship is rejected.

The result in Table 4 indicated that r_{cal} 0.791 is greater than r_{tab} 0.195. This implies that a significant relationship existed between mentoring strategy and teachers' job performance at 0.05 level of significance and 322 degree of freedom. Therefore, the null hypothesis of no relationship was rejected.

Table 3. Relationship between In-service Training Programmes and Teachers' Job performance.

Variables	N	Mean	SD	Df	r-cal	r-tab	Decision
In-service Training Programme	270	14.718	3.019				
Teachers' Job Performance	54	31.921	3.239	322	0.682	0.195	*

*Significant @ 0.05 (two tailed)

Table 4. Relationship between Mentoring Strategy and Teachers' Job Performance.

Variables	N	Mean	SD	df	r-cal	r-tab	Decision
Mentoring Strategy	270	18.988	2.917				
Teachers' Job Performance	54	32.322	3.007	322	0.791	0.195	*

*Significant @ 0.05 (two tailed)

DISCUSSION

Research question one examined the level of teachers' perception of in-service training strategy in public secondary schools in Ondo North Senatorial District. The results indicated that the respondents agreed that in-service training enhanced teachers' job performance. The reason is traceable to the fact that few respondents have been given opportunity to attend in-service training programmes in the last three years and many of the respondents have not been given the opportunity at all in the study area. This finding supported Aduke and Amudalat (2016) who revealed in a descriptive study that the capacity building for teachers was effective in areas of instructional delivery but not sufficient to sustain teachers in order to meet up with the changing needs in teaching profession.

Research question two showed that teachers were exposed to mentoring which improve capacity and that mentoring as a capacity building strategy was moderately used in the study area. This finding confirmed Moemeke et al. (2012) study which empirically discovered that mentoring has positive effect on mentees' teaching competency level.

Research hypothesis one investigated the relationship between in-service programme and teachers' job performance. The result of the finding revealed a significant relationship between in-service training and teachers' job performance which necessitated the rejection of the null hypothesis. The findings corroborated the outcome of the findings carried out by Yusuf et al. (2017) who found that teachers who had acquired workshop experience are more equipped and have the intellectual capacity to impact adequate knowledge on their students. The claim was in consonance with

Ogunrin (2011) who reported that teachers generally believe that in-service training programmes are very useful to them in terms of professional development, capacity building and productivity. With in-service training, teachers are exposed to new knowledge, techniques, and experiences added value to their teaching and nonteaching responsibilities. The finding of this study equally agreed with Asiyai (2016) who found that a significant number of teachers improved their knowledge of teaching approaches, using representations, models and diagrams and new questioning approaches after they were exposed to some capacity building strategies. The newly acquired teaching methods, skills and techniques could be responsible for the significant relationship between in-service training programme and teachers' job performance

Hypothesis two investigated the relationship between mentoring and teachers' job performance. The result revealed a significant relationship between the two variables which necessitated the rejection of the null hypothesis. It was concluded that a significant relationship existed between mentoring strategy and teachers' job performance. This finding confirmed the finding of Moemeke et al. (2012) who empirically discovered that mentoring has positive effect on mentees' teaching competency level. The level of competency of teachers after exposure to experienced mentors indicated that the use of experienced mentors often record better results. Furthermore, mentoring strategy was used to address issues related to teacher retention, professional development, support, building collegial relationships, adjusting inconsistencies in school policy implementation, and classroom problems. The researcher observed that what accounted for the positive effect of mentoring on the mentees was the use of informal mentoring which was

much in practice within the study area.

This finding also corroborated Achor and Duguryil (2014) that investigated the effectiveness of teacher mentoring programme in enhancing teacher's attitude towards the teaching profession. The study of Achor and Duguryil found that mentored teachers (experimental group) had higher mean post-test score than the control group. The difference in the analysis of covariance indicated that mentoring was effective in changing teachers' attitude towards the teaching profession.

CONCLUSION

It was concluded that in-service training strategy was inadequate while mentoring strategy was moderately used in improving teachers' job performance. However, both in-service and mentoring strategies contribute positively to teachers' job performance in public secondary schools in Ondo North Senatorial District, Nigeria.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings and conclusions drawn from this study, the following recommendations were made:

1. Government should encourage teachers to access capacity training within and outside the school by giving monetary assistance and due recognition to participants.
2. Principals should organise in-service training programmes for teachers and heads of department to address unusual problems relating to instructional delivery in school.
3. Principals should organise teacher mentoring programmes through the use of expert mentors to enhance the knowledge and skills of both mentors (within the school) and the mentees.

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